

A Study on Life Skills among Arts and Science College Students

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Life Skills are thus needed for the promotion of good health and well-being, rather than as an intervention aimed only at those already at risk. Life Skills are developed as a result of a constructive processing of information, impressions, encounters and experiences, both individual and social, which are a part of one's daily life and work, and the rapid changes that occur in the course of one's life".

The Life Skills Programme can be designed in such a way that it can be infused into other school subjects or it can be introduced as a new subject. Whatever design is followed, it must ensure greater potential for success. There are major changes and challenges associated with the period of adolescence, as youths acquire and consolidate on the social capital to make a successful transition into adulthood. This is particularly important as individuals begin to make choices and engage in a variety of activities that are influential on their lives.

In this work, the review, collection of data, Analysis and interpretation is done and the summary of findings are mentioned for future scope of work.

Review of literature

Athilakshmi, V., & Chitra, S. (2019). individual choose to communicate their message has an impact on the effectiveness of that message. It is essential to exchange ideas effectively for developing and sustaining relationship's the main purpose of every communication is to obtain some

ABSTRACT

The study investigated life-skills among college students. The respondents of the survey were 300 young adults aged 18 to 28 years from six colleges in Coimbatore. Life-skills Development Inventory-College Form was used to measure life skills in four domains: interpersonal communication, decision making, health maintenance and identity development. The findings revealed there is a significant in a study on life skills among arts and science college students with respect to College Locality, Type of Group and Parents Education and not with Gender, Medium of Instruction, Type of Family and Parents Income.

1. INTRODUCTION

For many individuals, the first year of college can be a very intimidating experience. Freshman university students often expect university life to offer them significant opportunities for personal, social, and intellectual growth. These opportunities require first year university students to adjust to the demands of a new adult independence in an entirely new environment. For student-athletes, the university life often results in experiences that can lead to heightened levels of stress and pressure due to their dual role of academics and athletics. For that reason it is important to provide student-athletes with an appropriate support system that will help them succeed during this transition.

Anyone who wants to lead a meaningful life needs Life Skills. They are applicable to all ages of children and adolescents, since young people in this age group seem to be the most vulnerable to behavior related health problems.

results, that is to secure action by the receivers.

Chakraborty, B., Maji, S., Sen, A., Mallik, I., Baidya, S., & Dwivedi, E. (2019). inquires about the relationship between a student's average happiness with her gender as well as the income class to which she belongs. It has been observed that among different aspects of social life, time spent with family and friends are significant while logging into social networking site is found out to be insignificant.

Thapar, R., Unnikrishnan, B., Kumar, N., Mithra, P., Kulkarni, V., Holla, R., & Bhagawan, D. (2019). innovative practices to reduce the effects of changing climate, and to the implementation of legislations the young people can contribute immensely. Materials and Method: In this cross-sectional survey 375 college students from Mangalore city were assessed regarding their perception, and attitude towards climate change and their practices towards mitigating it.

Nambiar, S., Jain, M., Unnikrishnan, B., Narayan, V., Babu, S., & Varghese, S. (2019). This metacentric study included 350 students from four dental colleges in India. Strong preference was calculated on Microsoft Excel using the VARK guidelines. Majority of the students were multimodal with many students showing two preferences.

Tilak, J. B. (2018). High rate of growth of higher education experienced in India, particularly since the beginning of the

1990s, is the alarming growth of private higher education. The size of the private sector is about twice that of the public sector in terms of the number of institutions and student enrolments.

Sachdeva, S. (2018). determine the prevalence of depression, anxiety, and stress among medical students. Students underwent face-to-face interview using predesigned, pretested, anonymous interview schedule using standardized survey instrument and Depression Anxiety Stress Scale 21 item.

Kumar, K. B., & Natarajan, S. (2018) The authors surveyed the HR alumni and HR managers to determine the relevance of HR curriculum of MBA program in meeting the requirements of various industries and identified that there is a big gap between the requirements of industries and availability of suitable candidates.

Bista, K., Sharma, G., & Gaulee, U. (2018). Increasingly become a key issue of policy and practice in higher education. This chapter presents a set of critical views about international student mobility globally, setting the context for emerging voices and critical lenses. The authors argue that educators should look into the bigger picture of mobility to understand its complex and multifaceted issues which go beyond counting enrollment numbers. Where do students go to study and why? Where do they come from and who was able to leave home? What obstacles do students face and how do they overcome them? There are some of the central questions of student mobility discourse. In this backdrop, the authors argue that students must be treated fairly by the simple logic of reciprocity: international students are “international” in the host countries in the same way as study abroad students will be “international” by default in the receiving countries. The only question is whether we are ready to accept a humane world where mobile students are valued as part of a global community and for global good, rather than just viewed in terms of mercenary drives of the market.

Jain, P. (2017). instructed all higher education institutions to go in for digital transactions. All universities authorities are instructed to take measures to stop cash transactions at

the campuses. UGC asked to organize “vittiya saksharta Abhiyan” campaign in the campuses to create awareness among students. The present study is focused on the impact of the cashless system on students, parents, and colleagues.

Garg, R., Goyal, S., & Singh, K. (2017). important in producing doctors with an understanding of evidence-based medicine. Though a mandatory part in post-graduate medical course, research has largely been invisible from the under graduation medical course in India. Very few research opportunities are available at under graduate level. The reason behind this is lack of encouragement, lack of basic infrastructure, facilities and structured mentorship programs, no extra incentives to researchers and the long journey to get academic acclaim. Another additional aspect is of lack of writing skills for biomedical publication. Additional incentives to students as well faculty members are required to foster the research environment in India.

Variables of the Study

In research, this term refers to the measurable characteristics, qualities, traits or attributes of a particular individual, object or situation being studied. Nurses use the term variable whether they are conducting, reading or using results of qualitative or quantitative research. Researchers often refer to variable by the terms dependent or independent. Dependent variable represent outcomes of interest and they are affect by independent (i.e predictor) variables. In this study, the investigator follows independent variable and dependent variables.

An independent variable is a variable that is expected to influence the dependent variables. Its value may be changed or altered, which is independent of any other variables. Also the following demographic variables were used as independent variables.

- Gender (Male/Female).
- College Locality (Rural/Urban)
- Medium of Instruction (Tamil/English).
- Type of Family (Joint/Nuclear).
- Type of Group (Arts/Science).
- Parents Education (Educated/Uneducated)
- Parents Income (Salaried/Self Employed)

Sampling Techniques

The sample which was collected from various colleges located in and around Coimbatore is shown as below.

TABLE 1 LIST OF SCHOOLS USED FOR DATA COLLECTION

S. No	Name of the Colleges	Number of students
1	Kongunadu Arts and Science College	43
2	KG College of Arts and Science	56
3	Sri Krishna Arts and Science College	55
4	PSG College of Arts and Science	50
5	Sankara College of Science and Commerce	51
6	Sri Ramakrishna Mission Vidyalaya College of Arts And Science	45
	Total	300

TABLE 2 DISTRIBUTION OF SAMPLES BASED ON VARIABLES

S. No	Category	Subgroups	Number	%	Total
1	Gender	Male	104	35	300
		Female	196	65	
2	College Locality	Rural	100	33	300
		Urban	200	67	
3	Medium of Instruction	Tamil	68	23	300
		English	232	77	

4	Type of Family	Joint	44	15	300
		Nuclear	256	85	
5	Type of Group	Arts	116	39	300
		Science	184	61	
6	Parents Education	Educated	153	51	300
		Uneducated	147	49	
7	Parents Income	Salaried	113	38	300
		Self Employed	187	62	

Research Tool

Tool become another major consideration in an education research. The instrument employed for the collection of data required for the study of any problem is called tool. "Tool employ distinction way of describing and qualifying the data" the important tools of educational research include interview schedule, questionnaire, observation, rating scale, achievement test, proficiency test, psychological tests and sociogram.

Hypothesis of the Study

1. There will not be a significant level of study on life skills among arts and science college students based on their Gender.
2. There will not be a significant level of study on life skills among arts and science college students based on their College Locality.
3. There will not be a significant level of study on life skills among arts and science college students based on their Medium of Instruction.
4. There will not be a significant level of study on life skills among arts and science college students based on their Type of Family.
5. There will not be a significant level of study on life skills among arts and science college students based on their Type of Group.
6. There will not be a significant level of study on life skills among arts and science college students based on their Parents Education.
7. There will not be a significant level of study on life skills among arts and science college students based on their Parents Income.

Analysis and Interpretation of Data

The analysis of data shall be done in this section and the results are mention in tables and charts

TABLE 3 Mean Score difference and t- value of factors related to significant study of level of study on life skills among arts and science college students based on their Gender.

S. No	Gender	N	Mean	Df	t-Value	P-value	Result
1	Male	104	1.4712	209	1.6522	0.1631	Accept
2	Female	196	1.5561				

CHART 1 LEVEL OF STUDY ON LIFE SKILLS AMONG ARTS AND SCIENCE COLLEGE STUDENTS BASED ON THEIR GENDER

TABLE 4 Mean Score difference and t- value of factors related to significant study of level of study on life skills among arts and science college students based on their College Locality.

S. No	College Locality	N	Mean	Df	t-Value	P-value	Result
1	Rural	100	1.2100	123	1.6573	0.0119	Reject
2	Urban	200	1.4900				

CHART 2 LEVEL OF STUDY ON LIFE SKILLS AMONG ARTS AND SCIENCE COLLEGE STUDENTS BASED ON THEIR COLLEGE LOCALITY

TABLE 5 Mean Score difference and t- value of factors related to significant study of level of study on life skills among arts and science college students based on their Medium of Instruction.

S. No	Medium of Instruction	N	Mean	Df	t-Value	P-value	Result
1	Tamil	68	1.5441	108	1.6591	0.0918	Accept
2	English	232	1.4267				

CHART 3 LEVEL OF STUDY ON LIFE SKILLS AMONG ARTS AND SCIENCE COLLEGE STUDENTS BASED ON THEIR MEDIUM OF INSTRUCTION

TABLE 6 Mean Score difference and t- value of factors related to significant study of level of study on life skills among arts and science college students based on their Type of Family

S. No	Type of Family	N	Mean	Df	t-Value	P-value	Result
1	Joint	68	1.5441	108	1.6591	0.0918	Accept
2	Nuclear	232	1.4267				

CHART 4 LEVEL OF STUDY ON LIFE SKILLS AMONG ARTS AND SCIENCE COLLEGE STUDENTS BASED ON THEIR TYPE OF FAMILY

TABLE 7 Mean Score difference and t- value of factors related to significant study of level of study on life skills among arts and science college students based on their Type of Group.

S. No	Type of Group	N	Mean	Df	t-Value	P-value	Result
1	Arts	116	1.3793	250	1.6510	0.0119	Reject
2	Science	184	1.5272				

CHART 5 LEVEL OF STUDY ON LIFE SKILLS AMONG ARTS AND SCIENCE COLLEGE STUDENTS BASED ON THEIR TYPE OF GROUP

TABLE 8 Mean Score difference and t- value of factors related to significant study of level of study on life skills among arts and science college students based on their Parents Education.

S. No	Parents Education	N	Mean	Df	t-Value	P-value	Result
1	Educated	153	1.3791	297	1.6500	0.0117	Reject
2	Uneducated	147	1.5238				

CHART 6 LEVEL OF STUDY ON LIFE SKILLS AMONG ARTS AND SCIENCE COLLEGE STUDENTS BASED ON THEIR PARENTS EDUCATION

TABLE 9 Mean Score difference and t- value of factors related to significant study of level of study on life skills among arts and science college students based on their Parents Income.

S.No	Parents Income	N	Mean	Df	t-Value	P-value	Result
1	Salaried	113	1.4248	238	1.6513	0.2589	Accept
2	Self Employed	187	1.4920				

CHART 7 LEVEL OF STUDY ON LIFE SKILLS AMONG ARTS AND SCIENCE COLLEGE STUDENTS BASED ON THEIR PARENTS INCOME

The various hypothesis as mentioned in previous section is analyzed based on the data collected and results are produced in tables 4-9 and charts 1-7. Respectively.

Summary of the Findings

A study on life skills among arts and science college students was studied and the findings reveal that there is a significant in a study on life skills among arts and science college students with respect to College Locality, Type of Group and Parents Education and no significant in a study on life skills among arts and science college students with respect to Gender, Medium of Instruction, Type of Family and Parents Income.

Conclusion

The conclusion is study on life skills among arts and science college students was studied and the findings reveal that there is a significant in a study on life skills among arts and science college students with respect to College Locality, Type of Group and Parents Education and not with Gender, Medium of Instruction, Type of Family and Parents Income

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PERSONAL DATA SHEET

APPENDICES

PROFORMA FOR BASIC DATA

1. Name of the Student :
2. Name of the College :
3. Gender : Male Female
4. College Locality : Rural Urban
5. Medium of Instruction : Tamil English
6. Type of Family : Joint Nuclear
7. Type of Group : Arts Science
8. Parents Education : Educated Uneducated
9. Parents Income : Salaried Self Employed

INSTRUCTIONS

- There are some statement below. Each statement is followed by multiple choice i.e. Yes /No.
- Read each Statement carefully.
- After reading each statement mark your response in the appropriate column pitting at tick mark

S. NO	QUESTIONARIE	YES	NO
1	I feel good about all the choices I make and try to make smart choices.		
2	I am a good friend and always respectful to my friends.		
3	Even if my friends pressure me to do something, I should do what I believe is right and say "no".		
4	I talk to my friends about problems I have because they can offer me help.		
5	I am a good leader because I help others make smart decisions.		
6	A good listener should not judge others, but try to understand how they feel.		
7	I always try manage my anger and I am never rude to my friends.		
8	When I make a decision I think about the good and bad things that can happen before making a decision.		
9	I think about my future goals and work hard each day to achieve them.		
10	I try to new skills and information which will help me reach my goals.		
11	When I have a conflict with friends, I always try to resolve it.		
12	I try and buy the things I "need" and not always buy the things I "want".		
13	It is very important to save money.		
14	Saving money is a smart way to plan for my future.		
15	It is important for girls my age to set goals about their future job.		
16	Social competence ability to relate to others.		
17	Critical/analytical thinking ability to consider issues from a range.		
18	Group/teamwork ability to co-operate with others and make a variety of contribution in a joint venture		
19	Computer literacy ability to use computer applications		
20	Self-assessment ability to evaluate your own strengths, weaknesses, progress and future learning objectives		

